

Recommendations for science communication under urgent and unexpected climate-related events

Main take-aways for science communication professionals

- Ensure messages are uniform, credible, factual, and non-politically biased to build and maintain public trust.
- Provide clear calls to action, encourage active involvement, and highlight consequences to motivate effective public response.
- Messages must be comprehensive, and simplified to convey complex information effectively, easy to locate, and widely disseminated across diverse, accessible channels for all audiences.
- Establish formal roles and co-create unified, scientifically accurate communication strategies with diverse stakeholders.
- Pre-allocate resources for communication, develop contingency plans, and conduct regular, inter-agency protocol simulations.
- Combat scepticism working with trusted messengers and promote climate and media literacy to fight disinformation.

Introduction

This report provides **actionable guidance** on how to improve science communication in the face of urgent and unexpected climate-related events. In particular, it addresses **critical aspects** such as establishing clear chains of action, developing coordinated communication strategies, prioritising proactive planning, tailoring approaches to diverse stakeholders, conducting practice runs, and integrating evidence-informed policy advice whilst balancing this with openness

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DESIGN AND TYPESETTING

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about inherent uncertainties in times of crisis. It also examines **barriers to effective urgent communication** and proposes **solutions**, emphasising the importance of consistency, engagement, completeness, accessibility,, and a focus on the impact of climate crises.

The [COALESCE project](#) has been investigating how science communication can contribute to **navigating complex, urgent societal issues** across multiple topics ([DeLong, K., et al., 2024](#)), offering different co-created tools and strategies, such as the [crisis navigator](#). As part of this work, we ran a participatory workshop titled “Climate Communication in Crisis Workshop: Co-creating Early Warning Strategies” held in Belgrade on October 1, 2025. The workshop was part of the [Climateurope2 festival](#), carried out under the framework of [Climateurope2 project](#), which focuses on the standardisation of climate services, fostering dialogue and collaboration in the climate services community. The workshop involved 8 participants and was structured into four parts. Part 1 focused on identifying key aspects and practical resources for urgent communication responses to climate crises. Part 2 and 3 addressed barriers and solutions for effective urgent communication. Finally, Part 4 focused on defining policy recommendations to address urgent science communication responses to climate crises.

Key aspects for efficient science communication under urgent climate crisis events

Science communication that is responding to urgent and unexpected climate crises requires careful consideration of several key communication features. For messaging to be targeted and achieve wide coverage, it must be sufficiently comprehensive to address all aspects of the crisis. This means it must include credible information, help navigate uncertainties and ambiguities,, be easily understood by everyone and

motivate effective responses. To achieve this it must include the following:

- **Reliable and consistent**
 - **Consistent:** Messages should be uniform across all platforms and over time to build trust and avoid confusion.
 - **Credible:** Both the source of the information and the message itself must be perceived as trustworthy, reliable, factual, and verifiable. To achieve this, focus on relational aspects, integrating two-way, dialogical science communication.
 - **Decouple from politics:** Where possible, communication should avoid presenting information in a way that appears to be biased towards a particular political agenda. Instead, the information should be presented neutrally and dependably, supported by facts and actionable insights rather than political rhetoric.
- **Action-oriented**
 - **Engaging:** Content should be relevant to hold audience's attention.
 - **Feasible:** Suggest actions that are practical and realistic to implement.
 - **Encourage action:** Communication should clearly instruct the audience on what steps they can take specially on imminent crises, but also on other phases. Providing concrete recommendations empowers individuals to respond effectively.
 - **Focus on possible consequences:** Communication should highlight the potential outcomes or impacts of climate crises to motivate action.
- **Accessible and findable**
 - **Audience reach:** Messages should reach a wide audience and be adapted to different needs, utilising various channels (social media, radio, TV, mobile phone) to ensure broad reach.
 - **Accessible:** Information should be available to everyone, including those with disabilities or limited access to technology, and without paywalls.
 - **Findable:** information should be easy to locate and access, especially that which is intended for imminent response.
- **Balance clarity on facts with values and emotions**
 - **Clear and simple:** Messages should be easily understood and presented in a straightforward manner.
 - **Values and emotions:** People assess information not just on evidence, but also on emotional and relational cues, making dialogue essential to foster inclusive, trustworthy science communication.

Barriers and solutions

When communicating during an urgent and unexpected climate-related event, several barriers exist. These can be categorised into five main areas: (1) Operational communication preparedness, (2) alert fatigue, (3) lack of resources, (4) scepticism towards climate science and institutions, and (5) message complexity and disinformation. Some solutions for these barriers are identified in the following table.

Main areas	Associated Barriers	Solutions
Operational communication preparedness	Uncertainty: Climate events are uncertain in their exact magnitude and timing.	Define guidelines with appropriate actions, and practice simulations. Deliver training to handle uncertainty in communicating crisis situations.
	Lack of inclusive communication.	Integrate good practices from other disciplines (i.e., behavioural science, visualisation, psychology) when developing and delivering messages; Consult people with disabilities and different impairments during the development process, to help identify the most appropriate formats and channels, ensuring information reaches diverse audiences in an equitable way.
	Contradictory information before the event can lead to confusion and lack of credibility.	Build capacity within the population to interpret and understand forecasts through dedicated training.
	Language in which information is conveyed.	Plan communication in multiple languages and consider the use of AI for optimisation of translation and message tailoring.
	Use of ineffective channels to convey messages. Rely on a single channel to convey information.	Use multiple communication channels/platforms and coordinated actions tailored to different audiences..
Alert fatigue	Overexposure to alerts , especially if they are perceived as false alarms or of low personal relevance, causes the public to become desensitised.	Improve effectiveness by establishing clear risk scales, universal alert systems, considering differences in thresholds. Perform user test evaluations to measure fatigue and find solutions on how to avoid it and when to send alerts.
Lack of resources	Insufficient budget , personnel, and time can affect the quality and effectiveness of communications.	Plan ahead: prepare coping tools, easy-to-understand preparedness resources and comms templates in advance, ensuring they are ready before an emergency strikes.
Scepticism in climate emergency, science and institutions	Lack of trust in institutions.	Work with trusted messengers. Instead of relying solely on official government spokespeople or scientists, identify and empower messengers who have credibility within specific communities. Use diverse expertise to build messages (science and communication experts). A collaborative process can turn raw data into a narrative that is both credible and relatable.
	Psychological denial of crisis.	Building climate literacy is a long term solution. This can be addressed by educating people on how the global issue connects to their local community and what they can do about it. This helps align public belief with the potential messages received during a crisis.
	Scepticism.	
	Lack of trust in science.	
Message Complexity & Disinformation	Intentional disinformation.	Liability in social media: hold social media companies to account, pressuring them to put in place procedures to minimise climate related disinformation.
		Adopt education strategies that address media and science literacy to empower citizens to be resilient to disinformation.
	Presenting complexity of the climate crisis in a univocal, clear-cut way can lead to confusion, inaction, or poor decision-making.	De-politise -> Localise: highlighting local solutions empowers people to take action, which may include civic activities and shifts the issue from a distant political debate. Use of Positive Narratives and Storytelling campaigns, similar to solutions journalism to provide a holistic view on climate crisis: Stories are memorable and convey complex information intuitively and from multiple perspectives.

Recommendations

Whilst crisis and risk communication management have clearly defined pathways, how science communication and science communication professionals can assist and be included in this process needs careful planning for effective coordination. Key recommendations to strengthen science communication include:

Mandate clear science communication roles: Establish a legal and administrative framework that defines the roles, responsibilities, and accountability of all entities (including scientific bodies) in climate crisis communication, ensuring a clear chain of action from data collection to message dissemination.

Develop unified science communication strategies: Co-create national/regional science communication strategies with diverse stakeholders (including scientific experts, science communicators and journalists) to ensure a unified, scientifically accurate messaging across all levels and platforms.

Proactively resource science communication preparedness: Mandate the pre-allocation of resources for communication preparedness, including development of plans for communicating scientific findings and potential impacts across all crisis phases.

Prioritise tailored and inclusive scientific communication: Support demographic research and vulnerability assessments to accurately identify stakeholder groups. Incentivise the use of communication tools and methods tailored to these specific audiences, focusing on strategies that are culturally sensitive, linguistically appropriate, and accessible through various channels. This must be reinforced by giving specific support and training to science communicators in delivering inclusive communication to ensure full readiness before an emergency strikes.

Standardise and test science communication protocols: Require regular, inter-agency simulations of communication protocols. Establish clear standards and indicators for the effectiveness of urgent communication of scientific warnings and findings, with mandatory post-event evaluation.

Integrate multidisciplinary scientific advice: establish permanent advisory mechanisms to formally integrate expert advice from climate science, communication, psychology, and social sciences into the development and execution of all climate communication strategies.

